

Developing a Task Model for Clinical Judgment in Nursing

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Outline

- Background Information
 1. Clinical Judgment in Nursing
 2. Assessment Model Development
- Task Model Development
- Item Development Process
 1. Item Writing Process
 2. Item Review Process

Background Information

Clinical Judgment in Nursing

- Increasing demand for clinical judgment skills among entry-level nurses
- Association between poor patient outcomes and poor nursing clinical decision-making (Nibbelink & Brewer, 2018).
- Only 20% of employers were satisfied with the decision-making abilities of new nurses (Berkow, Virkstis, Stewert, and Conway 2008)

Clinical Judgment in Nursing (cont.)

- Literature Review on Nursing Clinical Decision-Making (2012)
- NCSBN® & American Institutes of Research (AIR) collaboration (2013-2014)
 1. Functional Job Analysis
 2. Strategic Job Analysis
 - Linkage Workshop

Clinical Judgment in Nursing (cont.)

To what extent is the knowledge required in order to accomplish the task?

- 0 – Not Relevant for Performing the Task
- 1 – Helpful for Performing the Task
- 2 – Essential for Performing the Task
- DK – Don't Know

RN Tasks for Duty E

		E1	E2	E3	E4
		Discuss reproductive or sexual issues with client, such as family planning, menopause, erectile dysfunction, or gender identity.	Identify client immunization needs.	Perform routine, comprehensive health assessment.	Perform a targeted screening assessments, such as scoliosis, hearing, or vision.
Knowledge Statements	Knowledge Topics				
<h1>Skills</h1>		1	2	1	1
		DK	1	2	1
		2	2	1	1

Clinical Judgment in Nursing (cont.)

- Higher-order cognitive construct
 1. Challenging to define (Muntean, 2014)
- Accepted Models for Nursing Clinical Judgement
 1. Information Processing Model (see Elstein, Shulman, Sprafka and Allal 1978; Dickison et al, 2016; Dickison, Haerling and Lasater 2018)
 2. Humanistic-Intuitive Model (Benner 1982)
 3. Cognitive Continuum Model (Hammond, 1981; Harbison, 2001)

Overview of Model Development

Conceptual Model

Assessment Model

Observable Events

Assessment Model

Assessment Model

Assessment Model

Assessment Model

Task Model Development

Task Model

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
Recognize Cues		Recognize abnormal vs normal	Environment Cues:	
		Recognize signs and symptoms	Patient Observation Cues:	
		Identify history of	Medical Record Cues:	
			Time Pressure Cues:	Rationale
			Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

Task Model

				Scenario	
Recognize Cues		Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)		Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	
Identify history of		Recognize abnormal vs normal		Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	
Recognize signs and symptoms		Patient Observation Cues:		Environment Cues:	
Time Pressure Cues:		Medical Record Cues:			
Rationale		Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No		Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.	
Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.					

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.			
	Recognize Cues	Recognize abnormal vs normal	Environment Cues:				
		Recognize signs and symptoms	Patient Observation Cues:				
		Identify history of	Medical Record Cues:				
			Time Pressure Cues:			Rationale	
						Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

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	Analyze Cues	Connection between pathophysiology and client presentation:	Requires knowledge of:		
		Use findings/observations to determine client needs:		Rationale	
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

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	Prioritize Hypothesis	Prioritize (likelihood, risk, etc)	Requires knowledge of:			
			Indicate Resources:	Rationale		
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.	

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	Generate Solutions	Things to address:	Requires knowledge of:		
		Things to avoid:		Rationale	
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

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	Take Action	Request:	Requires knowledge of and experience with:		
		Administer:			
		Perform (Skill):			
		Document:			
		Communicate		Rationale	
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

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	Evaluate Outcomes	Reassess:	Requires knowledge of and experience with:		
				Rationale	
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Expected Behaviors	Checklist/Paraphrase (Layer 2)	Rules
Recognize Cues	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs
	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms
	Identify history of	Identify history of	Identify history of	Identify history of

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Expected Behaviors	Checklist/Paraphrase (Layer 2)	Rules
Analyze Cues	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs
	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Expected Behaviors	Checklist/Paraphrase (Layer 2)	Rules
Prioritize Hypotheses	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs
	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Expected Behaviors	Checklist/Paraphrase (Layer 2)	Rules
Generate Solutions	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs
	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Expected Behaviors	Checklist/Paraphrase (Layer 2)	Rules
Take Actions	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs
	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Expected Behaviors	Checklist/Paraphrase (Layer 2)	Rules
Evaluate Outcomes	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs	Recognize abnormal vital signs
	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms

Item Development Process

Item Development Process

Item Writing Process

- Item writing panels comprised 6-8 SMEs
- Facilitators provide ...
 1. Clinical judgment construct definition
 2. Definitions of layer 3 components
 3. Task model templates
 4. Practical examples and developed items

Item Writing Process (cont.)

- SMEs filled out the task model templates

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.	
	Recognize Cues	Recognize abnormal vs normal	Environment Cues:		
		Recognize signs and symptoms	Patient Observation Cues:		
		Identify history of	Medical Record Cues:	Rationale	
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Scenario & Item Writing Guidelines

- Scenarios must be realistic (high fidelity) & appropriate for entry-level nurse
- Items must measure the specific CJ element (training is provided)
- MR preferred (MC ok)
- Provide at least 6 response options per item
- Keys and distractors should be realistic
- Distractors could reflect:
 1. common errors associated with this scenario
 2. misconceptions about the topic
 3. critical misunderstandings and/or unsafe practices
 4. wrong associations with similar concepts
- In order for the candidate to answer the item, the candidate must refer to the scenario
- Other rules will apply for specific clinical judgment steps

Item Review Process

- Verifying that individual items written to each CJ element were truly measuring that element
 1. Reviewing the CJ scenarios
 - Entry-level nurse
 - Authentic/Realistic
 2. Reviewing individual items on the layer 3
 - Accuracy
 - Currency

Scenario & Item Review Criteria

Scenarios and item sets are to be:

- Clinically accurate scenario
- High-fidelity/authentic
- Appropriate for entry-level
- Current practice
- Items aligned with each clinical judgement step
- Answer key correct
- Avoid queuing across items in a set
- In scenarios do prior item responses imply item responses in following items

Item Finalization

- The scenarios and item sets from the item writing/review panels were developed into final items in different item/response format (or types)
- The next presentation will provide more details on a number of different item/response types that measure CJ elements

Scenario	Clinical Judgment (4 Apr 15)	Recognize Cues	Analyze Cues	Prioritize Hypotheses	Devise Plans	Evaluate Results
Recognize Cues		Recognize clinical cues	Recognize signs and symptoms	Identify history of		
		Environment cues	Pattern Observation cues	Medical Record cues		
			Team Presence cues	Equipment		
				External		
				Internal		
				Skills, CT		
				Step, Time		

Scenario	Clinical Judgment (4 Apr 15)	Recognize Cues	Analyze Cues	Prioritize Hypotheses	Devise Plans	Evaluate Results
Identify Problem(s)		Recognize clinical cues	Recognize signs and symptoms	Identify history of		
		Environment cues	Pattern Observation cues	Medical Record cues		
			Team Presence cues	Equipment		
				External		
				Internal		
				Skills, CT		
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Scenario	Clinical Judgment (4 Apr 15)	Recognize Cues	Analyze Cues	Prioritize Hypotheses	Devise Plans	Evaluate Results
Devise Plans		Recognize clinical cues	Recognize signs and symptoms	Identify history of		
		Environment cues	Pattern Observation cues	Medical Record cues		
			Team Presence cues	Equipment		
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				Internal		
				Skills, CT		
				Step, Time		

Scenario	Clinical Judgment (4 Apr 15)	Recognize Cues	Analyze Cues	Prioritize Hypotheses	Devise Plans	Evaluate Results
Evaluate Results		Recognize clinical cues	Recognize signs and symptoms	Identify history of		
		Environment cues	Pattern Observation cues	Medical Record cues		
			Team Presence cues	Equipment		
				External		
				Internal		
				Skills, CT		
				Step, Time		

Scenario	Clinical Judgment (4 Apr 15)	Recognize Cues	Analyze Cues	Prioritize Hypotheses	Devise Plans	Evaluate Results
Problem Resolved		Recognize clinical cues	Recognize signs and symptoms	Identify history of		
		Environment cues	Pattern Observation cues	Medical Record cues		
			Team Presence cues	Equipment		
				External		
				Internal		
				Skills, CT		
				Step, Time		

Scenario	Clinical Judgment (4 Apr 15)	Recognize Cues	Analyze Cues	Prioritize Hypotheses	Devise Plans	Evaluate Results
Problem Resolved		Recognize clinical cues	Recognize signs and symptoms	Identify history of		
		Environment cues	Pattern Observation cues	Medical Record cues		
			Team Presence cues	Equipment		
				External		
				Internal		
				Skills, CT		
				Step, Time		

Case Study Scenario 1.1	Recognize Cues	Analyze Cues	Prioritize Hypotheses
1.1			
1.2			
1.3			
1.4			
1.5			
1.6			
1.7			
1.8			
1.9			
1.10			

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